

Kaniadakis Distribution and $e/T \ll 1$ Considerations

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We argued in (1) that one may use $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ (where $p(e_i)$ is an unnormalized probability) and consider a single parameter ($k, -k$) power law for F which yields: $F(p) = \ln k(p)$ or $\ln q(p)$ in the Kaniadakis and Tsallis cases respectively. In the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit, a power law maps to an exponential which in turns maps to $1 - C e_i/T$ and so one easily obtains the possibility $1/2k$ (p power $k - p$ power $-k$). We also considered an alternative scenario which yields the Tsallis $\ln q$ function, also based on $-e_i/T$.

In general, the Tsallis case should yield Shannon results for $q=1$ and the Kaniadakis, for $k=0$. As a result, one may ask: Why should one consider the $e_i/T \ll 1$ scenario in the first place? We try to answer this question and show that k , in the Kaniadakis case, shows the shift of the second order power of (e_i/T) in a power expansion of $\exp(-e_i/T)$ (for $e_i/T \ll 1$). This possibly sheds some light on the meaning of k , at least in this limit.

Tsallis and Kaniadakis $\ln q$ and $\ln k$ Functions Tending to Shannon's \ln for $e_i/T \ll 1$

Tsallis $\ln q(p) \rightarrow$ Shannon's $\ln(p)$ for $q=1$ and Kaniadakis $\ln k(p) \rightarrow$ Shannon's $\ln(p)$ for $k=0$ ((1))

based on the way these are constructed. We have argued in (1) and elsewhere, that a starting point for Shannon, Tsallis and Kaniadakis analyses is:

$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((2)) where $p(e_i)$ is unnormalized and F is $\ln q$, $\ln k$ or \ln

The question then becomes: Why would one analyze ((2)) in the case of $e_i/T \ll 1$ and argue that one should obtain the Shannon \ln result when the a priori condition is ((1))?

We note first that the Tsallis and Kaniadakis approaches are single parameter (q in the Tsallis case, k and $-k$ in the Kaniadakis) power laws of $p(e_i)$ methods.

We note that: $\ln q(p) = \{p(e_i) \text{ power } q-1\} / (1-q)$ ((3)) (Tsallis) and that

$\ln k(p) = 1/(2k) \{ p \text{ power } k - p \text{ power } -k \}$ ((4)) (Kaniadakis)

Using ((2)),: $\exp q(e_i/T) = \{ 1 - (1-q)e_i/T \} \text{ power } 1/(1-q)$ ((5)) Tsallis and

$\exp k(e_i/T) = \{ \sqrt{1 + k k (e_i/T)(e_i/T)} + k e_i/T \} \text{ power } 1/k$ ((6)) Kaniadakis

As a result of the power law approach, one may consider the general solution, to first order in e_i/T , for $e_i/T \ll 1$ as:

$C1(k) + C2(k) e_i/T$ or $C1(q) + C2(q) e_i/T$ ((7))

For $k=0$, $C_1(k)=1$ and $C_2(k)=-1$ and for $q=1$, $C_1(q)=1$, $C_2(q)=-1$ ((8))

If one has only a linear expression in $p(e_i)$, i.e.

$\{1 + C_2(b) e_i/T\}$ power c then in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit: ((9))

$$= \exp(c C_2(b) e_i/T)$$

If one considers $k=1-q$ so that the Shannon result holds for $k=0$ ($q=1$), then if $C_2(b)=b$, $c=1/b$ which is the case in ((5)) and ((6)).

The next question one may ask is whether one may consider a higher order e_i/T term in ((9)) i.e.

$\{1 + b e_i/T + b^2 (e_i/T)(e_i/T)\}$ power $1/b$ ((10))

This is in fact the Kaniadakis case as one may see from ((6)).

The question then is: What is the condition on b^2 ? If $k=b$, then for $b \rightarrow 0$ ((10)) becomes:

$\exp(e_i/T + b^2/b e_i/T e_i/T)$ implying that $b^2/b=0$ or $b^2=b f(b)$ such that $f(b)=0$.

To seek the origins of this result, one may consider ((4)) with $p(e_i)$ given by $1 - e_i/T + b^2/b e_i/T e_i/T$ in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit. Thus, one has:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T = 1/2k \{ \exp(k(-e_i/T - b^2 e_i/Te_i/T)) - \exp(-k(-e_i/T - b^2 e_i/Te_i/T)) \} \quad ((13))$$

One may use $\exp(a) \approx 1+a$ for a small.

((13)) yields:

$$-e_i/T (2k) = 1 - k e_i/T - k b^2/2 e_i/Te_i/T + k k (e_i/T)(e_i/T) - \{ 1 + k e_i/T + k b^2 e_i/Te_i/T - k k/2 e_i/T e_i/T \}$$

$$-e_i/T (2k) = -e_i/T (2k) + 2 \{ -k b^2 - k k \} e_i/T e_i/T$$

$$\text{Thus, } b^2 = k. \quad ((14))$$

As a result, in the $e_i/T \ll 1$ limit,

$$\exp k(-e_i/T) = \{ 1 - k e_i/T + k k e_i/T e_i/T \} \text{ power } 1/k \approx 1 - e_i/T + k (e_i/T)(e_i/T) + \frac{1}{2} (e_i/T)(e_i/T) \quad ((15))$$

Thus, the linear k term shows how the quadratic term $(e_i/T)(e_i/T)$ deviates from the usual result in a power series expansion for $e_i/T \ll 1$.

The breaking of the Maxwell-Boltzmann $\exp(-e_i/T)$, then occurs for $e_i/T \ll 1$ at the quadratic $e_i/T(e_i/T)$ level with k being a measure of this break.

Thus, for $e_i/T \ll 1$, to first order one has MB result, $\exp(-e_i/T)$ and:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2) \approx \text{to first order } p(e_2)p(e_3) \text{ for } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \quad ((16))$$

In the Kaniadakis model, it is not only the $k=0$ situation that yields Shannon's results. To first order, for any k ($0 < k < 1$), one obtains Shannon's result $\exp(-e_i/T)$ for $e_i/T \ll 1$ and k shows the deviation of the $(e_i/T)(e_i/T)$ term from $\exp(-e_i/T)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Kaniadaikis (and Tallis) entropies are linked with a single absolute value parameter, with q being used for Tsallis and k , $-k$ for Kaniadakis (where one may associate $1-q = k$). In general, $q=1$ or $k=0$ yields Shannon results. We argue, however, that one may also obtain Shannon results if one considers e_i/T to first order. In the Kaniadakis case, a second order term in (e_i/T) appears in $\exp^k(-e_i/T)$ and we show that $+k(e_i/T)(e_i/T)$ is the deviation of the quadratic term in an $\exp(-e_i/T)$ expansion for $e_i/T \ll 1$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Obtaining the Tsallis Distribution from $e/T \ll 1$ and $e/T \gg 1$ Considerations? Part 2 (preprint,zenodo, 2025)